

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE RECOVERY AND RESILIENCE FACILITY IN THE BALKAN COUNTRIES

Vladi Kurshumov

Chief Assistant Professor, PhD, University of Economics – Varna, Bulgaria

Industrial Business and Logistics Department

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1153-4828>

Abstract

In recent decades, the European Union has made great efforts to support Member States in their development and competitiveness. This assistance is particularly important in the emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic, when national economies are facing a number of social and economic challenges. This study is focused on the implementation of the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) in the countries of the Balkan Peninsula. The scope of the study includes Bulgaria, Greece, Croatia, Romania and Slovenia. The scientific objective is to highlight the main characteristics of the National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRP) of the countries and to analyze the degree of their implementation, as well as their contribution to the achievement of pan-European policies, part of the RRF. The results show that Greece and Croatia are the most successful in absorbing funds, while Bulgaria reports serious delays in implementation.

Keywords: Recovery and Resilience Facility; European funding; European policies; Sustainable development; National Recovery and Resilience Plan

1. Introduction

The Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) is an instrument of the European Union with the main objective of helping Member States recover from the Covid-19 pandemic. As part of the NextGenerationEU plan, the RRF is based on striving to achieve a balance between green transition, digitalization and sustainable development, focusing on protecting the opportunity for future generations to live and develop in a suitable environment. The initial objective of the RRF when it was founded in 2021, related to overcoming the Covid crisis, is gradually expanding acquiring a much wider scope than the expected results, including social well-being, energy efficiency, competitiveness of businesses and national economies, etc. At a later stage, these objectives include overcoming energy market disturbances as a result of geopolitical instability, i.e. achieving integration with the EU's REPowerEU plan. The study focuses on the implementation of RRF in the countries of Bulgaria, Greece, Croatia, Romania and Slovenia. The aim of the research is to analyze and evaluate the implementation of the National Recovery and Resilience Plans by setting the following tasks for implementation: 1) Highlighting the main characteristics of the National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRP), including deriving the main directions of investment intentions and reforms; 2) Assessment of the level of implementation through analysis of the level of grants and loans disbursed; 3) A comparison of the achievements between the individual countries, as well as their contribution to the overall implementation of the European Union's sustainability policies. The research methods and approaches used include analysis, synthesis, comparison, induction, etc. Information from the official website of the European Commission is used, including statistics on disbursements by country.

2. General characteristics of the Recovery and Resilience Facility and National Recovery and Resilience Plans in Balkan countries

2.1. Characteristics of Recovery and Resilience Facility

Under the Recovery and Resilience Facility, Member States have access to significant financial resources with a view to achieving a package of measures and reforms at national level. Funding is provided through the implementation of projects that, together with the necessary reforms, are part of the National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRP). The total budget for the member states amounts to over EUR 650 billion for investments in reforms and projects, of which around 55% are in the form of grants and the remaining 45% are in the form of loans. To make these funds available, countries should implement their NRRP and commitments in stages, reflecting the readiness of individual economies to succeed in integrating the results of investments into their legislation, social and economic policies and the pursuit of sustainable development. The adopted concept of absorption of funds is based on actions and results, which suggests that only when specific measures and reforms are achieved, individual countries have the opportunity to absorb funding. During the period of operation of the RRF (2021-2026), there are a total of 9 intermediate stages of payments. Having in mind national specifics, over the years the degree of implementation of measures in different countries varies. Some manage to quickly implement commitments and absorb grants, while others have difficulties in making reforms, which delays the overall implementation of national plans and causes a number of risks, mainly related to non-absorption of the envisaged funding, a decrease in national competitiveness and a deterioration of the socio-economic situation.

2.2. Scope of National Recovery and Resilience Plans of Balkan countries

Bulgaria. Bulgaria's National Recovery and Resilience Plan includes investments amounting to EUR 6,185 billion, of which EUR 5,69 billion grant funding under the RRF. The plan does not provide funding in

the form of loans. The plan for Bulgaria focuses mainly on three directions: green transition – investments in decarbonization of the economy, energy from renewable energy sources and opportunities for its efficient storage, stability and safety of the energy system, etc.; economy transformation – investments in sustainable and environmentally friendly transport, digital connectivity, high quality education and healthcare, social inclusion, development of research, ensuring an impartial judicial system and a good business environment; social policy – strengthening the role and effectiveness in the work of institutions, fighting corruption, inclusive

education, improving the social security system, etc. The overall objective is to achieve the well-being of the population, including a better quality of life and a lower number of people in poverty; more sustainable employment of the population; a more sustainable and cleaner environment, less corruption and a more competitive economy and business. [1] Until April 2025, Bulgaria has managed to absorb only EUR 1,37 billion, which is part of the implementation of the first of all nine stages (first payment under the plan). The overall implementation rate amounts to 22,13 % (Table 1).

Table 1

Level of implementation of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of Bulgaria (April 2025)

Billion EUR	ALL EU Countries			Bulgaria			Bulgaria	
	RRF Loans disbursed	RRF Grants disbursed	Total	RRF Loans disbursed	RRF Grants disbursed	Total	% pilar/ total (Bulgaria)	% Bulgaria/ All EU Countries
Green transition	24,564	33,571	58,135	0	0,109	0,109	7,95%	0,19%
Digital transformation	14,978	25,031	40,009	0	0,171	0,171	12,50%	0,43%
Smart, sustainable and inclusive growth	33,401	46,489	79,89	0	0,280	0,280	20,45%	0,35%
Social and territorial cohesion	20,404	35,847	56,251	0	0,218	0,218	15,91%	0,39%
Health, and economic, social and institutional resilience	13,121	47,834	60,955	0	0,498	0,498	36,36%	0,82%
Policies for the next generation, children and youth, including education and skill	2,218	10,574	12,792	0	0,093	0,093	6,82%	0,73%
Total:	108,686	199,346	308,032	0	1,369	1,369	100,00%	0,44%

Source: Author's calculations based on data from European Commission [2]

The largest share of the absorbed funds by Bulgaria is in the "Health, and economic, social and institutional resilience" pillar (36.36%), followed by those in the "Smart, sustainable and inclusive growth" pillar (20.45%). Compared to the funds disbursed to all EU countries under the RRF, only 0.44% are those absorbed by Bulgaria.

Greece. Greece's National Recovery and Resilience Plan includes investments amounting to EUR 36,61 billion, of which EUR 18,22 billion in grants and EUR 17,73 billion in the form of loans under the RRF. EUR 13,6 billion are the funds allocated for the green

transition. In the field of economic transformation, the focus is mainly on the modernization and digitalization of public services for the population and the Greek economy. In the field of social policy, the focus is on supporting vulnerable groups and access to the labour market, modernizing healthcare and inclusive education and training. The overall goal is to improve the quality of life of the population, energy efficiency, digitalization of enterprises, etc. [3, 9] Until April 2025, Greece has received payments amounting to EUR 18.21 billion and has successfully implemented the reforms in the first 4 stages (Table 2).

Table 2

Level of implementation of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of Greece (April 2025)

Billion EUR	ALL EU Countries			Greece			Greece	
	RRF Loans disbursed	RRF Grants disbursed	Total	RRF Loans disbursed	RRF Grants disbursed	Total	% pilar/total (Greece)	% Greece/ All EU Countries
Green transition	24,564	33,571	58,135	2,538	1,6	4,138	18,63%	7,12%
Digital transformation	14,978	25,031	40,009	1,862	0,984	2,846	11,46%	7,11%
Smart, sustainable and inclusive growth	33,401	46,489	79,89	5,076	2,434	7,510	28,34%	9,40%
Social and territorial cohesion	20,404	35,847	56,251	0,139	1,431	1,570	16,66%	2,79%
Health, and economic, social and institutional resilience	13,121	47,834	60,955	0	2,002	2,002	23,31%	3,28%
Policies for the next generation, children and youth, including education and skill	2,218	10,574	12,792	0	0,139	0,139	1,61%	1,08%
Total:	108,686	199,346	308,032	9,615	8,590	18,205	100,00%	5,91%

Source: Author's calculations based on data from European Commission [2]

The largest share of the absorbed funds by Greece is in the "Smart, sustainable and inclusive growth" pillar (28.34%), followed by those in the "Health, and economic, social and institutional resilience" pillar (23.31%). Compared to the funds disbursed to all EU countries under the RRF, 5.91% are those absorbed by Greece. The implementation rate amounts to 49.73 %.

Croatia. Croatia's National Recovery and Resilience Plan includes investments amounting to EUR 10.00 billion, of which EUR 5.8 billion in grants and EUR 4.2 billion in the form of loans under the RRF.

Croatia's plan is defined as ambitious and comprehensive with its 78 reforms and 157 investment measures related to key areas of national social and economic policy. There is a focus on the green transition and the fight against climate change, as well as on support for education, health and social inclusion. [4] Attention is also paid to recovering the country from the earthquakes in 2020, investments in the modernization of kindergartens and schools, independence of the electricity system, etc. (Table 3).

Table 3

Level of implementation of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of Croatia (April 2025)

Billion EUR	ALL EU Countries			Croatia			Croatia	
	RRF Loans disbursed	RRF Grants disbursed	Total	RRF Loans disbursed	RRF Grants disbursed	Total	% pilar/total (Croatia)	% Croatia/ All EU Countries
Green transition	24,564	33,571	58,135	0,2155	0,618	0,834	16,74%	1,43%
Digital transformation	14,978	25,031	40,009	0,0284	0,474	0,502	12,84%	1,26%
Smart, sustainable and inclusive growth	33,401	46,489	79,89	0,2868	0,8587	1,146	23,26%	1,43%
Social and territorial cohesion	20,404	35,847	56,251	0,1895	0,6146	0,804	16,65%	1,43%
Health, and economic, social and institutional resilience	13,121	47,834	60,955	0,071	1,058	1,129	28,66%	1,85%
Policies for the next generation, children and youth, including education and skill	2,218	10,574	12,792	0,0047	0,0682	0,073	1,85%	0,57%
Total:	108,686	199,346	308,032	0,7959	3,692	4,487	100,00%	1,46%

Source: Author's calculations based on data from European Commission [2]

The largest share of the absorbed funds by Croatia is in the "Health, and economic, social and institutional resilience" pillar (28.66%), followed by those in the "Smart, sustainable and inclusive growth" pillar (23.26%). Compared to the funds disbursed to all EU countries under the RRF, 1.46% are those absorbed by Croatia. The overall implementation rate amounts to 44.87% and the first 5 stages were successfully completed.

Romania. Romania's National Recovery and Resilience Plan includes investments amounting to EUR 28.5 billion, of which EUR 13.6 billion grants and EUR 14.9 billion in the form of loans under the RRF. The

plan is defined as sustainable, socially oriented and focused on the transformation of the national economy. Some of the more important reforms are the decarbonization of the energy sector, the development of renewable energy, improving access to water, education and healthcare by improving infrastructure. [5] Among the investment intentions are also support for disadvantaged groups, transition to green transport, reducing dependence on fossil fuels, etc. Until April 2025, Romania has absorbed a total of 33.13% of the funds, part of the first two stages of the Plan's implementation (Table 4).

Table 4

Level of implementation of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of Romania (April 2025)

Billion EUR	ALL EU Countries			Romania			Romania	
	RRF Loans disbursed	RRF Grants disbursed	Total	RRF Loans disbursed	RRF Grants disbursed	Total	% pilar/total (Romania)	% Romania/ All EU Countries
Green transition	24,564	33,571	58,135	0,797	0,454	1,251	7,86%	2,15%
Digital transformation	14,978	25,031	40,009	0,299	1,23	1,529	21,28%	3,82%
Smart, sustainable and inclusive growth	33,401	46,489	79,89	1,589	0,7605	2,350	13,16%	2,94%
Social and territorial cohesion	20,404	35,847	56,251	0,5975	0,8157	1,413	14,11%	2,51%
Health, and economic, social and institutional resilience	13,121	47,834	60,955	0,2972	2,043	2,340	35,35%	3,84%
Policies for the next generation, children and youth, including education and skill	2,218	10,574	12,792	0,0825	0,4761	0,559	8,24%	4,37%
Total:	108,686	199,346	308,032	3,6622	5,779	9,442	100,00%	3,07%

Source: Author's calculations based on data from European Commission [2]

The largest share of the absorbed funds by Romania is in the "Health, and economic, social and institutional resilience" pillar (35.35%), followed by those in the "Digital transformation" pillar (21.28%). Compared to the funds disbursed to all EU countries under the RRF, 3.07% are those absorbed by Romania.

Slovenia. Slovenia's National Recovery and Resilience Plan includes investments of EUR 2.7 billion, of which EUR 1.62 billion in grants and EUR 1.05 billion in the form of loans under the RRF. The focus of the

plan is primarily on achieving a climate-neutral economy, including through sustainable mobility and renewable energy. Other investment intentions are related to achieving resilience to natural disasters, reforms in the field of healthcare, pension system, as well as inclusive education and training. [6] Until April 2025, Slovenia had absorbed a total of 40.69% of the funds, part of the first three stages of the Plan's implementation (Table 5).

Table 5

Level of implementation of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of Slovenia (April 2025)

Billion EUR	ALL EU Countries			Slovenia			Slovenia	
	RRF Loans disbursed	RRF Grants disbursed	Total	RRF Loans disbursed	RRF Grants disbursed	Total	% pilar/total (Slovenia)	% Slovenia/ All EU Countries
Green transition	24,564	33,571	58,135	0,1453	0,149	0,294	22,16%	0,51%
Digital transformation	14,978	25,031	40,009	0,0194	0,1056	0,125	15,70%	0,31%
Smart, sustainable and inclusive growth	33,401	46,489	79,89	0,0291	0,1915	0,221	28,48%	0,28%
Social and territorial cohesion	20,404	35,847	56,251	0,155	0,108	0,263	16,06%	0,47%
Health, and economic, social and institutional resilience	13,121	47,834	60,955	0,0387	0,0865	0,125	12,86%	0,21%
Policies for the next generation, children and youth, including education and skill	2,218	10,574	12,792	0,0387	0,0318	0,071	4,73%	0,55%
Total:	108,686	199,346	308,032	0,4262	0,672	1,099	100,00%	0,36%

Source: Author's calculations based on data from European Commission [2]

The largest share of the absorbed funds by Slovenia is in the "Smart, sustainable and inclusive growth" pillar (28.48%), followed by those in the "Green transition" pillar (22.16%). Compared to the funds disbursed to all EU countries under the RRF, 0.36% were those absorbed by Slovenia.

3. Main results and discussion

Level of implementation (due to the grants and loans disbursed)

The results show that the NRRP is implemented to the greatest extent by Greece, which as of April 2025 has absorbed 39.73% of the envisaged funds. In second place is Croatia with 44.87%, followed by Slovenia with 40.69% and Romania with 33.13%. Bulgaria ranks last in terms of implementation with only 22.13% and only one stage of the plan has been completed. This information is indicative that Bulgaria faces serious risks of losing financial resources and the inability of the country to succeed in implementing the envisaged reforms and policies and integrating all expected results into its social and economic policy within the framework of the RRF.

Contribution to the pan-European implementation of the RRF

The 5 countries examined in the study together managed to absorb EUR 34.6 billion. This is 11.23% of the funds disbursed all countries. By comparison, the share of the total funds available to these 5 countries from the total EU budget under the RRF amounts to 12.9%. This shows that the Balkan countries are implementing the plans relatively evenly compared to the whole budget.

Of interest is the contribution of the Balkan countries in the implementation of the areas of intervention (pillars). **Green transition:** the share of the total absorption of funds in this pillar by the Balkan countries amounts to 11,4% of the total funds disbursed to all European countries. Greece is leading with 7,12%, and

Bulgaria reports the lowest relative share with only 0.19%. **Digital transformation:** the share of the total absorption of funds in this pillar by the Balkan countries amounts to 12,93% of the total funds disbursed to all European countries. Again, Greece is leading with 7,11%, and Slovenia reports the lowest relative share with only 0,31%. To a large extent, this is explained by Slovenia's relatively small budget as a whole. **Smart, sustainable and inclusive growth:** the share of the total absorption of funds in this pillar by the Balkan countries amounts to 14,40% of the total funds disbursed to all European countries. Greece is leading with 9,40%, and Slovenia reports the lowest relative share with only 0,28%. **Social and territorial cohesion:** the share of the total absorption of funds in this pillar by the Balkan countries amounts to 7,59% of the total funds disbursed to all European countries. Greece is leading with 2,79%, and Bulgaria reports the lowest relative share with only 0,39%. **Health, and economic, social and institutional resilience:** the share of the total absorption of funds in this pillar by the Balkan countries amounts to 10,00% of the total funds disbursed to all European countries. Romania is leading with 3,84%, while Slovenia reports the lowest relative share with only 0,21%. **Policies for the next generation, children and youth, including education and skill:** the share of the total absorption of funds in this pillar by the Balkan countries amounts to 7,30% of the total funds disbursed to all European countries. Romania is leading with 4,37%, while Slovenia reports the lowest relative share with only 0,55%, followed by Croatia (0,57 %). In the case of Slovenia, it should be noted that low values of the indicator do not mean poor implementation of the plan. On the contrary, Slovenia shows a comparative balance between the commitments made and national specificities, applying for a smaller budget that is implemented to a greater extent.

4. Conclusion

Undoubtedly, the Recovery and Resilience Facility has been assisting Member States in their recovery from the crises of recent years. At the same time, national differences have led to an unbalanced use of available financial resources. Some countries have been more successful in implementing the planned reforms, so as to provide their population with an improved quality of life and standard of living. Other countries, due to various macroeconomic factors, are lagging significantly behind the general European development [7]. In the context of pursuing sustainable development and care for future generations, these countries risk reducing their competitiveness. More targeted actions are needed in the absorption of European funds. This can be achieved with better planning of measures and investments and the involvement of a wider range of stakeholders, including Civil Society Organizations, that have an important role in key decision making processes (in case of Romanian's NRRP, [8] It is also important in this case to prioritize the planned reforms so that they ensure balanced development and greater utility for society, while at the same time ensuring the implementation of achievable goals and strategies given the macroeconomic situation.

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